

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

THE IDENTIFICATION OF CAUSATIVE ORGANISM, HOW MUCH THEY ARE SUSCEPTIBLE TO ANTIBIOTICS & TO DETERMINE SEPTIC ARTHRITIS FREQUENCY¹Dr Yumna Riaz, ²Dr. Junaid Khalid, ³Dr. Anam Sahar¹House Officer DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala, ²UHS, Lahore, ³Mayo Hospital Lahore.**Article Received:** December 2018 **Accepted:** February 2019 **Published:** March 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: The research objective is the determination of Septic Arthritis frequency, susceptibility of Causative Organisms (*Staphylococcus Aurous*) to antibiotic like ceftriaxone and its identification.

Material and Methods: We conducted this cross-sectional study at OPD of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (January to September 2017). We included both gender patients having (14 – 60) year's age with swollen joint, joint pain, and fever. We excluded patients with open joint injury, post-elective surgery infection, tuberculosis infection, and dry taps.

Results: We found SA among 37% patients out of 73 patients. The number of male and female patients was 52.10% (38) and 47.90% (35) respectively. Knee joint and hip, were involved among 89% (65) and 11% (08) cases respectively whereas elbow was not involved in any case. We found 79.50% cases susceptibility to ceftriaxone and the involvement of *Staph. Aurous* with 72.60% patients.

Conclusion: We found SA among males more comparing to females whereas it can occur at among any age-group. Knee joint has the common-most involvement in SA. Ceftriaxone was the most susceptible drug and *Staph. Aurous* was the common-most isolated organism.

Keywords: Septic Arthritis (SA), Synovial Fluid (SF), Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE), *Staphylococcus Aurous* (*Staph. Aurous*) and Rheumatoid Arthritis (RA).

Corresponding author:

Dr. Yumna Riaz,
House Officer DHQ Teaching Hospital Gujranwala.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Yumna Riaz et al., *The Identification Of Causative Organism, How Much They Are Susceptible To Antibiotics & To Determine Septic Arthritis Frequency.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(03).

INTRODUCTION:

This is one of the common medical emergencies that a patient is presented with a single or multiple hot-swollen joint. The diagnosis of such symptoms has a broad-differential, where SA is its serious, though not typical, cause. The mortality and morbidity rate of this disease is high [1]. The annual incident rate of SA in US is 10/100,000 individuals and becomes one of the common-most like RA or prosthetic-joint (70/100,000 individuals) [2]. Patients with HIV (Human Immunodeficiency Virus) are also highly susceptible to non-gonococcal SA [2]. The common-most target of SA is knee joint with 50% cases. Elbow, hip, and shoulder are also at high risk (in frequency ascending order) of SA, although the risk exists for any particular surface [3]. As synovial tissue has no basement membrane, therefore, entrance to SF becomes easier for Bacterial organism, thus hematogenous spread becomes the cause of most cases [4]. Therefore, it is essential to diagnose and manage SA with appropriate anti-biotic as infection can destroy cartilage in days and the mortality rate of a treated infection at hospital can be high up to 15% [2]. Delayed diagnosis and presentation can lead to increase in mortality and permanent disability. Previous researches suggest that in most cases, synovial tests, physical examination, clinicians, and history can help in inferring etiology of acute non-traumatic mono-articular arthritis within three days. Since during an emergency of patients with mono-articular arthritis, physicians never get three-day admission time, therefore, identifying important diagnostic-findings in differentiation of non-septic from SA accurately becomes essential in minutes and hours [2, 5]. If we conceptualize quantitatively, the clinical decision-making range of probability of disease goes from (0%-to-100%) [6]. Multiple factors like elements of past/present medical examination, therapeutic responses, lab studies and imaging make the health providers revise disease-probabilities continually [7]. Dr Pauker and Dr Kassirer presented a theoretical model for test and treatment-threshold computation in 1980. This algebraic equation by Pauker-Kassirer gives an estimate for the division of patients into 3 groups: Group-1 includes probability of disease below the test-threshold where further diagnosis through test will be more harmful than useful, Group-2 includes probability of disease is at intermediate between treatment-threshold and test so further diagnostic test will be beneficial, and Group-3 includes the probability of disease exceeding treatment-threshold where further diagnostic tests will present risks through therapeutic delay or diagnostic test resulting in unintended consequences [8, 9]. SA is a common infection among our population. This study aims to develop a data to provide guidelines in the

reduction of irrational anti-biotic use. At the same time develop resistance to anti-biotic and use of pathogens and how much they are susceptible to anti-biotic. SA refers to count of WBC in SF is more than (50000 Cells/mm³).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

We conducted this cross-sectional study at OPD of Jinnah Hospital, Lahore (January to September 2017). We included both gender patients having (14-60) year's age with swollen joint, joint pain, and fever. We excluded patients with open joint injury, post-elective surgery infection, tuberculosis infection, and dry taps. After receiving ethical approval from International Review Board, we selected patients fulfilling inclusion criteria and took their informed, written consent. We took SF by taping the joint taking guidance from ultrasound. We sent the sample to lab for naked-eye examination (hemorrhage, colour, and consistency), Microbial (WBC, TLC, DLC, RBC, Gram-Staining, ZN-Staining, sensitivity, etc.), and Chemical (level of protein and glucose) examinations. The reports identified etiological agent, its sensitivity, and culture. We used pre-designed Pro-forma to record etiological agent and selection of drug from the sensitivity and culture reports. This helped us in identifying the organism and the drug which is susceptible to it. We also included demographic data (age, gender, and joint type) in the Pro-forma.

We used SPSS for data record in the computer. We calculated mean and Standard Deviation for quantitative variables (age). We presented qualitative variables (gender, joint type, SA) as percentages and frequency. To control the effect-modifiers, we used stratification of gender, age, RA, and SLE. We applied Chi Square test, took (P-value \leq 0.05) as significant.

RESULTS:

We used SPSS to enter/analyse patients' (73) data. The mean age was (45.0 \pm 12.9) years. We found 37% (27) patients with SA among 73 patients. We found 72.60% (53) and 79.50% (58) patients with the involvement of etiological agent (Staph. Aurous) and susceptibility of ceftriaxone respectively. We found 61.60% (45) patients with RA among 73 patients. For age stratification, we divided patients into Group-A (14 – 37 years) and Group-B (38 – 60 years). In Group-A, consisting of 34.66% (18) patients, we found 50% (09) patients with SA but found no significant association with age and SA with (P-value = 0.260). The number of male and female patients was 52% (38) and 47.9% (35) respectively. We found SA among 34.2% (13) and 40% (14) male and female patients respectively. There was insignificant association between SA and

gender with (P-value = 0.640). Among type of joints, we found knee joint and SA among 89.0% (65) and 38.4% (25) patients respectively. Among 10.9% (08) patients with the involvement of hip joint, we found SA among 25% (02) patients. There was no association between joint type and SA. Among 61.6% (45) patients of RA, we found SA among 31.1% (14)

patients with no association between SA and RA. After the stratification of SLE, we found 66.6% (02) patients with SA among 4% (03) patients with SLE. Among patients (70) without SLE, we found 35.70% (25) patients with SA. The association between SLE and SA was insignificant with (P-value = to 0.550).

Table – I: SA, EA, Cef and RA frequencies

Frequency		Number	Percentage
Septic Arthritis	Yes	27	37
	No	46	63
Etiological Agent (Staphylococcus Aurous)	Yes	53	73
	No	20	27
Susceptibility to Ceftriaxone	Yes	58	79
	No	15	21
Rheumatoid Arthritis	Yes	45	62
	No	28	38

Table – II: Variables Stratification

Variables		Yes		No		Total		P-Value
		No	%	No	%	No	%	
Age	14 – 37 Years	9	50	9	50	18	24.66	0.26
	38 – 60 Years	18	32.73	37	67.27	55	75.34	
Gender	Male	13	34.21	25	65.79	38	52.06	0.46
	Female	14	40	21	60	35	47.94	
Joint Type	Knee	25	38.46	40	61.54	65	89.04	0.46

	Hip	2	25	6	75	8	10.96	
	Elbow	0	0	0	0	0	0	
Rheumatoid Arthritis	Yes	14	31.11	31	68.89	45	61.64	0.22
	No	13	46.43	15	53.57	28	38.36	
Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)	Yes	2	66.67	1	33.33	3	4	0.55
	No	25	35.7	45	64.3	70	96	

DISCUSSION:

We recorded the mean age of patients as 45 years whereas Li SF et al. found 53 years as mean age among SA patients, which in contrast to our study [10]. On the other hand, Weston et al. shows agreement to our study [11]. We found 37% patients with SA among 73 patients in our study. The study of Li SF et al. is not in favour with our findings, however, Nutt et al. shows similar results with 29% patients having SA [10, 12]. Our study shows male dominance with SA which is in agreement with the study of Kaushik et al. in Kuwait and Fahmi et al. [13, 14]. Our study shows knee joint to be the most affected by SA with 89% patients. This outcome is in agreement with the study of Abid et al., Kaushik et al., and Uthman et al. [15, 13, 16]. Among the causes of SA, our study finds Staph. Aurous to be the common-most (72.60%) etiological agent. The studies of Yadav et al. (62%), Abid et al., and Nahman et al. show similar outcomes with Staph. Aurous to be the common-most organism, causing SA [17, 15, 18]. The study of Kalantari et al. shows similar (60.50%) results to our study [19]. On the other hand, the study of Arnold et al. shows results in contrast with H. influenza as the common-most cause of SA [20]. In our study, we found Ceftriaxone susceptible among 79.50% which shows similarity with the study of

Yadav et al. which shows 83% Ceftriaxone susceptibility [17].

CONCLUSION:

We found SA more among male comparing female patients with specificity with age-group. The common-most joint was Knee joint, with Staph. Aurous to be the common-most isolated organism and ceftriaxone was the susceptible-most drug.

REFERENCES:

1. Abid N, Bhatti M, Azharuddin M, Islam M. Septic arthritis in a tertiary care hospital. JPMA. 2006;56(3):95.
2. Uthman I, Bizri AR. Clinical features of septic arthritis at a tertiary care hospital in Lebanon. Clin Rheumatol 2003; 22:359-60.
3. Yadav S, Dhillon MS, Aggrawal S, Tripathy SK. Microorganisms and Their Sensitivity Pattern in Septic Arthritis of North Indian Children: A Prospective Study from Tertiary Care Level Hospital. ISRN Orthopedics. 2013; 2013:1-4.
4. Nahman A, Hammoudeh M. Pyogenic Arthritis in Qatar. Qatar med J.2003; 2:36-9.
5. Kalantari N, Taherikalani M, Parvaneh N, Mamishi S. Etiology and Antimicrobial Susceptibility of Bacterial Septic Arthritis and

- Osteomyelitis. Iranian Journal of Public Health. 2007;36(3):27-32.
6. Arnold SR, Elias D, Buckingham SC, Thomas ED, Novais E, Arkader A, et al. Changing patterns of acute hematogenous osteomyelitis and septic arthritis: emergence of community associated methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. *J Pediatr Orthop*. 2006 Dec;26(6):703-8.
 7. Revell PA. The synovial biopsy. In: Antony PP, Sween M, Lowe DG. editors. *Recent Advances in Histopathology-13*. New York: Churchill living stone; 1987. p. 79-83.
 8. Mc Carty DJ. Synovial fluid. In: Koopman WJ editor. *A Text book of Rheumatology*. 14th ed vol (1). Philadelphia: Lippincott Williams and Wilkins; 2001. p 83-104.
 9. Segovia AD. Descriptions of therapeutic arthrocentesis and of synovial fluid. In a Nauhatal text from per Hispanic Mexico. *Ann Rheum Dis* 1980; 39:291-3.
 10. Amer H, Swan A, Dippe P. The utilization of synovial fluid analysis in the UK. *Rheumatology* 2001; 40:1060-3.
 11. Li SF, Cassidy C, Chang C, Gharib S, Torres J. Diagnostic utility of laboratory tests in septic arthritis. *Emergency Medicine Journal*. 2007 Feb 1;24(2):75-7.
 12. Weston VC, Jones C, Bradbury N, Fawthrop F, Doherty M. Clinical features and outcome of septic arthritis in a single UK Health District 1982-1991. *Ann Rheum Dis* 1999; 58:214-9.
 13. Nutt L, Orth H, Goodway J, Wasserman E. Superior detection of pathogens in synovial fluid by the Bactec 9240 Peds Plus/F system compared to the conventional agar-based culture method: original research. *Southern African Journal of Epidemiology and Infection*. 2010;25(4):11-4.
 14. Kaushik P, Malaviya AN, Rotimi VO. Infective arthritis in adults – experience at a teaching hospital in Kuwait. *Rheumatology International*. 1999 Dec 1;19(1-2):1-5.
 15. Khan FY, Abu-Khattab M, Baagar K, Mohamed SF, Elgendy I, Anand D. et al. Characteristics of patients with definite septic arthritis at Hamad General Hospital, Qatar: A hospital-based study from 2006 to 2011. *JCR*.2013:1-14.
 16. Tercic D, Bozic B. The basis of synovial fluid analysis. *Clinchem lab Med* 2001;39: 1221-6.
 17. Eisenberg M, Schumacher H, Davidson P, Kauffmann L. Usefulness of synovial fluid analysis in the evaluation of joint effusions. Use of threshold analysis and likelihood ratios of access a diagnostic test. *Arch Int Med* 1984; 144:715-9.
 18. Shmerling RH. Synovial fluid analysis. A critical reappraisal. *Rheum Dis North Am* 1994; 20(2): 503-12.
 19. Sangeetha B, Vora IM, Abraham S, Srivastava S, Jignesh S, Chaturvedi R. Role of synovial fluid analysis and synovial biopsy in joint diseases. *bjh. Org. Journal* 2004.
 20. Donge DR, Brouwer R, Smit M, Frankinjer M, Dulhain RJ, Toorenbergen V. Automated counting of white blood cells in synovial fluid. *Rheumatology* 2004; 43: 170-3.